

Source: [Heravi, M.M.](#), Daraie, M. (2016), Mn(pbdo)2Cl2/MCM-41 as a green catalyst in multi-component syntheses of some heterocycles, Journal of Research on Chemical Intermediates, 42(4), [doi: 10.1007/s11164-015-2191-2](https://doi.org/10.1007/s11164-015-2191-2)

Mn(pbdo)2Cl2/MCM-41 as a green catalyst in multi-component syntheses of some heterocycles

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Abstract

Mn(pbdo)2Cl2/MCM-41 as a solid acid catalyst was used as an efficient, green, reusable catalyst for an improved and rapid one-pot multi-component reaction in the synthesis of bis-(4-hydroxycoumarin), bis(indolyl)methane, and 4H-benzo[b]pyran derivatives.

Keywords

4H-benzo[b]pyrans, Bis(indolyl)methanes, Catalysts, Bis-(4-hydroxycoumarin) derivatives, Mn(pbdo)2Cl2/MCM-41, Multi-component reactions, Solid acid catalysts, Methane, 4-Hydroxycoumarin, Manganese